

**A STUDY ON EFFECTIVENESS OF COUNSELLING
AMONG THE STUDENTS IN DHANALAKSHMI
SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR**

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Cite This Article: N. Suguna, E. Deepak Metha & J. Jaisurya, "A Study on Effectiveness of Counselling Among the Students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 71-73, 2022.

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Abstract:

Comparison of college students, 2 years after referral for intensive counseling, indicated that the group in which counseling had been accepted make definite gains in scholastic achievement in contrast to the group in which the need for help was defined or the group that failed to see a counselor at all. Background the are demands of academic life are considered to be increasingly stressful for students in higher education. But there is limited research about extent to which those attending students counseling services experience difficulties relating to academic issues and how effective counseling is for them.

Introduction:

Counseling is an art and science. It's a short term, interpersonal, theory based, helping profession. Its aim is to resolve developmental and situational difficulties. Counseling helps to bring change in life: Change in thought; Change in emotion; and Change in behaviour. Both the American Counseling Association (ACA) and Division 17 (Counseling Psychology) of the American Counselors are members of organizations that set professional and ethical standards and promote state licensing and certification by national associations (Wittmer & Loesch, 1986). The process of certification and licensing and the adherence to ethical codes assure the public that the Psychological Association (APA) have defined counselling on numerous occasions. Their definitions contain a number of common points, some of which follow. Counseling is a profession. Practitioners should complete a prescribed course of study usually leading to a master's degree or a doctorate degree. Counselor meets minimal educational and professional standards. Counselors should possess personal qualities of maturity, empathy, and warmth. Overall, counseling is active and differs considerably from passively listening to problems.

Studies on Guidance and Counselling:

Guidance Programme, like any other educational programme, requires careful and consistent development. This ensures that the programme responds to the unique Needs of its clients. It provides benefits to students by addressing their intellectual, emotional, social and psychological needs. It is important that today's guidance and counselling programme to be developmental, so that it assists students who are growing up in a complex world.

It should help them to develop into full human beings, capable of maximizing their Kumari (2013) in the article "significance of imparting guidance and counselling programmes for adolescent students" revealed the need for developing guidance and counselling programme for adolescent students for enhancing life competencies and solving problems.

The article indicated that the guidance and counselling plays a vital role for preventing educational, personal, social, mental, Bozgeyglg, Huseyin and Erciyes (2010) examined the effect of computer assisted career group guidance to levels of self-efficacy of 8th grade elementary school students. Research is an experimental study which is based on experiment and control group pre-test and, post-test model. Computer assisted career guidance was made with experiment group students for 5 weeks in two sessions. In total 10 sessions Asaf, Athar, Muhammad and Amir (2010) conducted a study to investigate the educational guidance services at secondary schools of Rawalpindi.

The guide provides a model for such programs and a process for tailoring the model to meet the varying needs of students Texas Educational Agency (2004) prepared a model comprehensive, developmental guidance and counselling program for Texas public schools, a guide for program development pre-k -12th grade has been developed to help ensure that all students in Texas might benefit from high quality comprehensive, developmental Assisted career group guidance to levels of self-efficacy of 8th grade elementary school students.

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sessions. In total 10 sessions Asaf, Athar, Muhammad and Amir (2010) conducted a study to investigate the educational guidance services at secondary schools of Rawalpindi.

Objective of Study:

- A study on effectiveness of counselling among the students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College Perambalur.
- To Study the awareness about the counselling section among the students.
- To Study the effectiveness of counseling process in our college.
- To Study the counselling beneficial among the students.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is a systematic way to solve the research problems. It gives an idea about various steps adopted by the researcher in a systematic manner with an objective to determine various matters.

Research Design:

The main aim of the study is to know the utilization of library among the student in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College. A research design is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data. Regarding this study, descriptive research design concerned with describing the each individual's perception on utilization of library. Hence the research design is descriptive in nature.

Descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. The characteristics used to describe the situation or population.

Sampling Design:

- Sampling Technique Simple Random Sampling
- Sample Size 240
- Population 2272
- Sample Area Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College

Tool for Data Collection:

Primary Data:

The primary data was obtained by questionnaire method.

Statistical Tools Used:

- Percentage Method
- Chi-Square Test
- Correlation Method
- Anova Table

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Showing Awareness about the Counseling System:

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	28	11.66
2	Agree	122	50.83
3	Neutral	74	30.83
4	Strongly Disagree	4	1.66
5	Disagree	12	5
	Total	240	100

Inference:

The table that 11.66% of the respondents are strongly agree, 50.83% of the respondents are agreed 30.83% of the respondents are neutral,1.66% of respondents are strongly disagree,5% of the respondents are disagree.

Findings:

- From the Percentage Analysis it was found that
- Majority 43% of the respondents are under the age of 19 years old.
- Majority 63.3% of respondents are female.
- Majority 78% of respondents are Hostellers.
- Majority 65.83% of respondents are aware about the counselor and students.
- Majority 50.83% of respondents are agreed that college is free from counseling.
- Majority 41.66% of respondents are agreed about the counseling system of college.
- Majority 46.66% of respondents are agreed that counseling is effective one.

Suggestions:

Every slier lining has a cloud: relapse and the symptoms of sobriety, by (Scott Stevens.)A significant number of students experience varying levels of stress, anxiety homesickness, and depression which may negatively impact their academic performance or personal functioning. However, many college students do not seek professional help from campus counselor. The result of the study suggest that, even where academic reason are not the primary cause of referral to students will also experience difficulties in these areas.

Conclusion:

As evident in the research, more debate is needed about the problems and constraints encountered for introducing and implementing Guidance and Counseling in schools. More theoretically oriented qualitative research has to be done in guidance and counseling, especially research based on life skills and personality development an approach that is a vital key to improvement in practice. Guidance is a process not a product as its heart is not only meeting people's immediate wants, but also helping them to clarify their long-term needs. The main objectives of the guidance and counseling programmed should be the maximum development of the individual and the entire programmer should be organized keeping in mind this purpose.

References:

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